

EFFECT OF ORAL MOTOR INTERVENTION (PIOMI) ON FEEDING PROGRESSION AND LENGTH OF HOSPITAL STAY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW PROTOCOL

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Abstract

Introduction: The feeding development of preterm infants are different from that of term infants. As, the motor skills of preterm infants are underdeveloped and lack coordination between sucking and swallowing with respiration. This coordination helps in oral feeding progression and apnea prevention, aspiration, bradycardia as well as hypo-oxygenation. For better development there should be complete sucking as well as swallowing activity. The introduction of PIOMI is to control the movement for the lips, cheeks, jaw and tongue by increasing functional pressure to stimulate with finger strokes in specific movement. It is a specific motor intervention that is focused on 5 minute 8-steps protocol for lips, jaw and tongue. The feeding rehabilitation protocol of preterm infants will help in better development of infants and early hospital discharge. **Aim:** The main objective of this review is to assess the effectiveness of pre term infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) on Physiological stability and length hospital stay among preterm infants. **Methods:** A systematic review on randomized control trails, and non-randomized control trails will be conducted. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-analysis (PRISMA) will be adopted and literature search will be conducted in Pub Med-Medline, CINAHL, Science Direct and ProQuest. The search will include a period of 2010-2023. Studies will be included based on predetermined inclusive criteria. **Results:** A descriptive synthesis of the findings of the selected studies will be carried out which will be presented in narrative summary with statistical findings incorporated. **Conclusion:** This review will provide evidence to support or reject the hypothesis that whether oral motor stimulation (PIOMI) among preterm infants supports physiological stability, feeding progression and early discharge from hospital.

Keywords: Hospital Discharge, Length of Stay, Physiological Stability, PIOMI, Preterm Infants, Weight Gain.

INTRODUCTION

Infant mortality rate plays an important indicator to reflect upon the health status of any country. As per WHO, preterm infant are the babies who are born before 37 weeks of gestation or in less than 9 months. Preterm birth have significantly increased even in developed countries since past 20 years. Out of 25 million children taking birth in India per year, about 1.7 million of preterm births are at high risk of death in early period of development.¹ Apart from prematurity, other factors that can severely impact the morbidity of such babies are poor sucking/swallowing coordination and difficulty in temperature regulation due to large body surface area leading to hypothermia. Due to immaturity of taking oral feed, pre mature babies suck-swallow-breathing coordination is impaired and this directly affect the vital organs like lungs, heart, brain.²The poor development of these major organ causes various problems like delay in growth and development, feeding desaturation, impaired pulmonary functions etc. Premature babies poor survival is common scenario in developing countries due to lack of basic medical facilities like warmth, breastfeeding support, and prevention of sepsis and support during breathing difficulties. Initiation and maintenance of oral feeding as well as physiological stability are considered as main health determinants that is causing longer hospital stays and higher medical cost for families. The feeding progression is the phase when infant is able to take more than 80 percent of total prescribed feed orally in 24 hours.³ It requires proper suck- swallow-breath cycle. Many researchers have supported the implementation of various stimulation techniques for hospitalized preterm infants to provide as close as intrauterine environment for the babies especially in their first week of life.⁴

The preterm infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) is relatively emerging technique of stimulation developed by Dr. Brenda Lessen. It includes stimulation of oral musculature to enhance contraction as well as resistance of muscles in and around oral structure.⁵ This technique is derived from BOMI (Beckman oral motor intervention), which is a complete set of step by step intervention lasting for total 15 minutes especially done for neonates, older children and even adults facing issues of developmental delay with problems of feeding.⁶ The major drawback of BOMI is its unsuitability for premature infant due to their smaller oral cavity posing difficulty to perform 15 minutes intervention time on tongue, palate, gums (upper and lower) etc. So, PIOMI is the modified version of original BOMI to include just 8 steps and lesser time of 5 minutes as per tolerability level of premature infants beginning from 29 weeks PMA. Few modified steps included to accommodate small oral structure of premature babies. After thorough examination PIOMI can be provided by healthcare workers, occupational therapist, neonatologists, parents and other developmental specialists after undertaking a formal training. As per different studies it has not shown adverse effects on babies after implementation.⁷

There is emerging global interest PIOMI due to consistent success rate in reducing transit time to full oral feeding among preterm babies, but it differs in cultural variations that is limiting its external validity.⁸ hence, continuous testing of the intervention is required in different cultures, setups and communities. Although studies have demonstrated the

benefits of oral intervention on gaining of weight, stable vitals etc. Thus, protocol is planned for assessing the usefulness of oral stimulation among preterm hospitalized infants.

Rationale

Preterm infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) is 5 minute protocol for preterm babies. This protocol is designed especially for preterm infants very small oral cavity tolerance. It include nonnutritive sucking also and can be performed successfully on babies as early as 29 weeks PMA⁹. Also, it can be taught to parents after training to fulfill the motive of parental involvement during child care in hospital. Hence researcher felt it necessary to examine randomized and non randomized control trials to assess the usefulness of newer protocol PIOMI among preterm babies in terms of better oral development, readiness to take feeding orally, and gain in weight and hospital discharge.¹⁰

Objectives

To determine the benefits of preterm infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) on feeding progression and length of hospital stay among preterm infants.

METHODS

All the steps will be followed as per PRISMA guidelines¹¹. The review is already registered under the International Prospective Register for Systematic Review (**PROSPERO Registration No. CRD42023443584**).

Criteria for Eligibility

As per protocol total three steps will be adopted while searching for literature review including only English language research papers between 2010-2023.

1. Preterm infant oral motor intervention, oral stimulation, multi-sensory stimulation, oral massage, preterm infants, very low birth weight babies will be searched in pubmed-Medline, CINAHL plus other databases using keywords

P - Preterm infants

I - Preterm infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI)C-Routine care

O-Health Benefits for the baby such as better oral motor coordination, improvement in weight, progression towards oral or breast feeding, decreased hospital stay and reduced medical cost. The abstract and titles of the studies retrieved from literature will be analyzed using appropriate keywords.

2. Additional keywords will be utilized for detailed search in major databases like Cochrane library, Ovid, Pubmed, Scopus, Science Direct, Medline and CINAHL.
3. In the final steps, references given in major research articles will also be scrutinized to retrieve relevant studies.

The criteria will be used to select studies for this review is mentioned below.

- a) Research articles that are published in peer review journals only.
- b) All the accessible research papers from e- databases.
- c) *Study design*: Only RCT and non RCT will be accommodated in this protocol
- d) *Intervention*: Implementation of premature infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) on clinical stable hospitalized premature infants.
- e) *Settings*: Neonatal intensive care units, newborn nurseries
- f) *Outcomes*: To find out the benefits of premature infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) on physiological stability (improvement of feeding orally or weight gain) and early hospital discharge among premature infants
- g) *Language*: English only research papers
- h) Studies that have used terms like PIOMI or oral motor stimulation among premature infants will be taken. As per guidelines from JBI (Joanna Briggs Institute) manual the relevant studies will be screened. Before uploading the studies to Zotero/ Mendeliner reference programme any duplicate article will be removed. The topic under review will be evaluated thoroughly in terms of titles and abstracts. After the independent screening from two authors for relevancy of abstract or full text any discrepancy will be accommodated by the third author
- i) *Exclusion criteria*: Abstract from conferences, only abstract or grey literature and books content.

Sources of Information

The major databases will be searched using the keywords as per PICO, then the particular abstract and titles will be searched using similar words. Further detailed investigation will be done by using clear approach from science direct databases, CINAHL plus databases, pubmed-Medline, Cochrane library.

Search Strategy

Science Direct Databases:

PIOMI OR oral stimulation AND Premature infants AND Physiological stability AND Length of stay AND {Randomized Control Trials} Filters: Original articles, Year; 2010-2023

Pubmed:

(PIOMI) OR (physiological stability) AND (Length of hospital stay), Randomization controlled trial results: Research articles, Year; 2010-2023

Study Records

Data management. The study paper will be uploaded in Zotero software as well as elimination of duplicated research articles will be done. The details of articles will be maintained within reference manager throughout the review.

Selection Process

The headings and abstract of research article will be assessed with the help of two authors during the screening procedure as per the applicability of review. The complete content will be reviewed as per eligibility requirements. The scrutinization of abstract and full texts will be done independently and any disagreement throughout the screening process will be resolved with the consultation with the third author.

Data Collection Process

The guidelines as per JBI (Joanna Briggs Institute Manual)¹² will be followed for clinical appraisal of chosen research papers. Two reviewers will be directly involved in scrutinization of research articles, any disagreement will be resolved with help of third reviewer. The data from relevant research studies will be extracted from Cochrane databases.

Data Items

The research studies with variables like preterm infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) effect on feeding progression, weight gain, oral feeding readiness, early hospital discharge, physiological stability among preterm infants as study population

Outcome and Prioritization

In this review the main outcome will be effect of PIOMI on feeding progression, weight gain, oral feeding readiness, early hospital discharge, physiological stability among preterm infants. So, providing oral motor intervention to preterm infants will be the main review outcome.

Assessment of Individual Bias Risk

Cochrane risk bias assessment will be adopted to evaluate individual study for randomized controlled trials (RCTs)¹³

Data Synthesis

The findings of the study will be based on the objectives formulated. The summary will include both descriptive synthesis and statistical findings from the studies. SMD (Standardized Mean Difference) will be utilized for meta-analysis of the selected variables like feeding progression, weight gain, oral feeding readiness, early hospital discharge, physiological stability and I² statistics will be used to measure heterogeneity.

Assessment of Publication Bias

Publication bias will be analyzed for the research articles included in this review.

Cumulative Evidence Confidence

The GRADE pro¹⁴ approach will be used to assess the certainty of evidence.

CONCLUSION

This review is developed with the objective of understanding preterm infant behaviors. Additionally, providing insights related to preterm infant stimulation that helps in improving transition time for oral feeding, weight gain and length of hospital stay. The clinical parameters of preterm infants can be improved if this intervention is utilized successfully in hospitalized babies. Nurses are the primary care provider to neonates admitted in hospital with prematurity. So, it is essential to educate them regarding PIOMI that may help in decreasing medical cost on family and nation as a whole.

References

- 1) Zheng, W., Chotipanvithayakul, R., Ingviya, T., Xia, X., Xie, L., & Gao, J. (2022). Sensory stimulation program improves developments of preterm infants in Southwest China: A randomized controlled trial. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 867529. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.867529>
- 2) Aranha, V. P., Chahal, A., & Bhardwaj, A. K. (2021). Short-term effects of multimodal stimulation on neuromotor behaviour and neonatal pain among hospitalized preterm infants: A feasibility, non-blinded randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Neonatal-Perinatal Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.3233/NPM-210889>
- 3) Vaivre-Douret, L., Oriot, D., Blossier, P., Py, A., Kasolter-Péré, M., & Zwang, J. (2009). The effect of multimodal stimulation and cutaneous application of vegetable oils on neonatal development in preterm infants: A randomized controlled trial. *Child: Care, Health and Development*, 35(1), 96–105. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2214.2008.00895.x>
- 4) Lessen Knoll BS, Daramas T, Drake V. Randomized controlled trial of a prefeeding oral motor therapy and its effect on feeding improvement in a Thai NICU. *JOGNN-J Obstet Gynecol Neonatal Nurs* 2019; 48:176–88.
- 5) Jyoti, Kodi, S. M., & Deol, R. (2023). Effect of Premature Infant Oral Motor Intervention on Oral Feeding and Weight Gain: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Iranian journal of nursing and midwifery research*, 28(3), 225–234. https://doi.org/10.4103/ijnmr.ijnmr_341_21
- 6) Iran, Mahdieh, S., Rahnama, M., Ghaljaei, F., Akbarizadeh, M. R., Naderifar, M., & Zabol, Iran. (2021). The effect of multisensory stimulation on weight gain in premature infants admitted to the intensive care unit: A clinical trial study. *Romanian Journal of Neurology*, 20(1), 96–102. <https://doi.org/10.37897/RJN.2021.1.13>
- 7) Lessen, B. S. (2011). Effect of the Premature Infant Oral Motor Intervention on Feeding Progression and Length of Stay in Preterm Infants. *Advances in Neonatal Care*, 11(2), 129–139. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ANC.0b013e3182115a2a>
- 8) Shokri, E., Zarifian, T., Soleimani, F., Knoll, B. L., Mosayebi, Z., Noroozi, M., & GhasrHamidi, K. (2022). Effect of premature infant oral motor intervention (PIOMI) combined with music therapy on feeding progression of premature infants: A randomized control trial [Preprint]. In Review. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-2066214/v1>

- 9) Shailaja S.Jaywant et.al. The effect of pre-feeding protocol with and without tactile and Kinaesthetic stimulation on oral motor ability & physiological stability in preterm infants.
- 10) International Journal of Health Sciences and Research Vol.11; Issue: 1; January 2021
- 11) Majoli, M., De Angelis, L. C., Panella, M., Calevo, M. G., Serveli, S., Knoll, B. L., & Ramenghi, L. A. (2023). Parent-Administered Oral Stimulation in Preterm Infants: A Randomized, Controlled, Open-Label Pilot Study. *American Journal of Perinatology*, 40(08), 845–850. <https://doi.org/10.1055/s-0041-1731452>
- 12) Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, et al. The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews. *BMJ*. 2021; 372: n71. Doi: 10.1136/bmj. n71
- 13) Tufanaru C, Munn Z, Aromataris E, Campbell J, Hopp L. Chapter 3: Systematic Review of Effectiveness. In: Aromataris E, Munn Z, editors. *JBIManual for Evidence Synthesis* [Internet]. JBI; 2020 [Cited 2020 Nov 9]. Available from: <http://wiki.jbi.global/display/MANUAL/Chapter+3+A+Systematic+reviews+of+effectiveness>.
- 14) RevMan. Version 5.3. Cochrane Training. Accessed November 12,2022. <https://training.cochrane.org/online-learning/core-software/revman>
- 15) GRADEpro GDT, GRADEpro Guideline Development Tool [software]. McMaster University: 2015 (developed by Evidence Prime Inc.) Available from grade.pro